

Jessica Dello Russo

Jewish Antiquities in Eighteenth Century Rome: The *Corpus Inscriptionum Judaicarum* 1.1.

Ἀμελίω τέκνω γλυκυ
τάτω ὄς ἔζησ
εν ἔτη β', μῆν
ας β', ἡμέρας
ε'. Ἀμέλις ἄρχω
κε Μαρία γονεῖς τέ
κνω ἀμωμω ὀσειῶ.
ἐποίησαν.

The inscription CIJ 1.1, a child's funerary epitaph in Greek, was first published by Father Antonio Lupi, S. J. in his *Dissertatio ed animadversiones ad nuper inventum Severae Martyris epitaphium*, Palermo, 1734, p. 140 (figure). As noted by Father Antonio Ferrua, S.J., all known copies of the inscription up to the present time depend on Lupi's edition.¹ Lupi locates the piece "in villa d.d. Sinibaldi ad Flaminiam," within the late Renaissance gardens of the Sinibaldi family on the right side of the via Flaminia between the Porta del Popolo and the Villa Giulia on the first mile outside of Rome.² Lupi states where the inscription could be seen, not necessarily where it had first been discovered.³ His study contains only this one inscription from the site, apparently displayed separately from the bulk of the Sinibaldi family's collection of antiquities housed inside their cluster of palaces on the via del Mascherone in Rome.⁴

The inscription copied by Lupi uses several common funerary formulae. The deceased is characterized in lines 1-2 as "sweet" (γλυκυτάτω), the life span is specified in years, months, and days, and the donors of the monument are named along with their relationship to the deceased.

Yet a number of irregularities in the text are also immediately apparent. In lines 2-3, ἔζησεν is written for ἔζησεν (a rare variation, found also in CIG 3.6442); the word ἄρχω in line 5 is a singular

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In Villâ D.D. Sinibaldi, ad Flaminiam; non procul a Porta, quam a
Populo vulgò dicunt, vidi hanc Inscriptionem Græcam, ἀμειλίω τέκνω
ἐπιτάφια κειμένη:

Inter lapides quosdam literatos, qui inventi sunt, ante annos non ita
multos Corneti, nunciatum mihi fuit & hunc sepositum, rudem, atque
impolitum:

Sed

[1] Videtur explicari posse: *Amelio*
Filio dñicissimo; qui vixit annos
duos, Menses duos, Dies quinque:
Amelii, Archon, & Maria (cor-
rigo namque Ἀμελίου ἄρχων, & Μαρία)
Parētes, Filio meo Museo fecerunt.

Non plane intelligo vocabulū
ἀμειλίω, nisi explicetur: Meo
suavi: sicuti Lucretius dicit lib.
primo, Museo coniungens multa
lepore, id est suavi & Musarum
proprio.

¹ A. Ferrua, *Addenda et Corrigenda al Corpus Inscriptionum Judicarum*, in *Epigraphica*, 3 (1941), pp. 31-32.

² F. Luccini & R. Pallavicini, *La Villa Poiniatowski e la via Flaminia*, Rome, 1981, p. 47.

³ F. Luccini & R. Pallavicini, *La Villa Poiniatowski e la via Flaminia*, Rome, 1981, p. 47.

⁴ CIJ 1, p. 6, classifies n. 1 as having been found in that area of the via Flaminia. Lupi's entry, however, does not make this a certainty. More recently, Claudia Ferro has raised the possibility that the piece came from a 1734 excavation in a "vigna Sinibaldi" near the Coliseum: again, however, nothing explicitly links the piece to this particular site: "Sarcophago a lenos con iscrizione sepolcrale del fanciullo Ἀμέλιος" (n. 233) in *I marmi antichi di Palazzo Rondinini*, ed. D. Candilio & M. Bertinetti, Rome, 2011, p. 218.

⁵ F. Lombardi, *Palazzi, Palazzetti e Case di Roma, 1200-1870*, Rome, 1992, p. 371 (on the via del Mascherone e via Torre Argentina/vicolo Sinibaldi).

Villa Strozzii Sinibaldi

Auf einem kleinen Cenotaphio ist die Figur eines un-
 kleideten jungen Menschen, der sich mit beyden Händen eine
 Binde um die Stirn bindet mit der Unterschrift
 DIADVMENI

oben stehet

D. M. ext. ap. Murator.

Auf den Seiten der Figur

TI. OCTAVI.

Auf der einen Seite des Cenotaphii
 unter einem aufgehängten Crantz

A D
 P I
 N V M⁹⁹⁷

Auf der anderen Seite stehet eine Fuße

Die Buchstaben sind zierlich u. scheinen von guter Zeit

Auf einer kleinen Urne von schlechter Arbeit

ΑΜΕΛΙΩ ΤΕΚΝΩ ΓΑΥΚΥ ext. ap. Murator. MCXXIX. 6.⁹⁹⁸

ΤΑΤΩ· ΟΣΕΖΖΗC

ΕΝ ΕΤΗ Β ΛΛΗΝ

ΑC· Β· ΗΜΕΡΑC

Ε ΑΜΕΛΙCΑΡΧΩ

ΚΕΛΛΑΡΙΑ ΤΟΝΕΙC ΤΕ

ΚΝΩ ΑΜΜΩΜΩ ΟCΕΙΩ

ΕΠΟΙΗCΑΝ.

abbreviation for the nominative form of the title ἄρχων; and another abbreviated word starts line 6: κε for και.⁵

The adjective ὄσιος in line 7 is written as ὄσειω. Lupi, in the end, has great difficulty interpreting this line, the most “crowded” of the text, finally reading the letters ἄμμωμω as two words: “meo museo.”

Later scholars were not able to verify Lupi’s transcription, but the recent publication of Johannes Joachim Winkelmann’s 1756 notebook, *Ville e Palazzi di Roma*, includes a previously unknown copy of the same text of even greater value than that of Lupi because of its care to reproduce the appearance of the original.⁶ The letters are shown to be somewhat irregular in terms of size and spacing, but most of the individual words seem complete.⁷ Yet Winkelmann does not add much in the way of commentary, stating only that the inscription was “auf einer kleinen Urne von schlechter Arbeit” (“on a small urn of poor workmanship”). In itself, however, this detail may be

significant. Winkelmann is the only scholar to mention that the epitaph was found on an urn, a term also used to describe a container or sarcophagus.

Lupi, on his part, identifies the piece as pagan or “ethnic” rather than Jewish. But his *Dissertatio* does include a number of Jewish inscriptions on sarcophagi in private houses and churches, as well as in the museum organized by members of his own order, the Jesuits, in Rome.⁸ Two of the sarcophagi he illustrates are very

generic in production, and identified as Jewish only from the inscriptions naming a *pater synagogae* and a *gerusiarch* (figure).⁹ Another marble fragment, part of a sarcophagus lid, is inscribed with Greek and Hebrew phrases to commemorate a certain Faustina, accompanied by images of the Jewish *shofar*, *menorah*, *lulab*, and

⁵ H. J. Leon, *The Jews of Ancient Rome*, Philadelphia, 1960, p. 73, calls this abbreviation the sign of an “indistinguishable dipthong.” A. E. Felle counts 34 examples in Christian inscriptions from Rome in *Inscriptiones Christianae Urbis Romae n.s. Concordantia e verborum, nominum et imaginum. Tituli graeci*, Bari, 1997, pp. 146-147. A brief discussion of these variations is also in Ferro’s article in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011, p. 217.

⁶ J. J. Winkelmann, *Ville e Palazzi di Roma*, ed. J. R. Serra, Rome, 2000, p. 200.

⁷ Ferro in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011, p. 217.

⁸ CIJ 1.504/JIWE 2.558 and CIJ 1.508/JIWE 2.544 published by Lupi, 1734, p. 51 nn. 7.1-2. Lupi is the only reliable source for the latter (now missing).

⁹ *Infra*, n. 8.

ethrog (CIJ 1.283/JIWE 2.535).¹⁰

In the second volume of his *Novus Thesaurus veterum inscriptionum* (1740), Lodovico Antonio Muratori also passes neutral judgement on the text, reading in line 5 a *duonominia* for the father: “Ἀμελῖς Ἀρχων.” Yet later authors from the mid-eighteenth century down to the present are nearly unanimous in viewing the inscription as Jewish (or, to a small minority, Christian) from the identification of the father, Ἀμελῖς as an ἄρχων, the term for a synagogue official most commonly used at Rome, and the problematic words in line 7, corrected by Gregorio Piacentini to read ἀμμομω and ὁσεῖω, “immaculate” and “holy.”¹¹

The inscription itself “disappears” after the mid-eighteenth century, but is included in nearly all the studies and collections of Jewish inscriptions in Rome following the recovery of a number of examples from the Monteverde catacomb in 1748. Recent studies on Jewish epigraphy have also re-examined CIJ 1.1 in the context of all funerary texts from Rome. David Noy believes that the father’s title and possibly Semitic name of the mother, Maria (Μαρία), in line 6 are strong indications of a Jewish text.¹² Leonard V. Rutgers, in *The Jews of Late Ancient Rome*, is even more convinced that the use of the title of ἄρχων and the adjective ὁσεῖω (l. 7) characterize this piece as a Jewish inscription.¹³ The title of ἄρχων, “magistratus,” is indeed that most frequently cited in Jewish inscriptions from Rome.¹⁴ Noy, however, carefully notes a number of exceptions to this rule, and excludes from his syllogism a Greek inscription mentioning an *arcontikos* buried in a columbarium of the freedmen Cosutii in the Vigna Moroni, and another apparently mentioning one “Ἀρχων” by name.¹⁵

As a Jewish epitaph, CIJ 1.1, is exceptional on many counts. It lacks the epigraphic formula and images that were used in a significant number of the Jewish epitaphs from Rome. The Greek name Ἀμελῖς or Ἀμέλιος for both father and son is, for this area, unique.¹⁶ Μαρία, “Maria”, the mother’s name, is more commonly used in this context, but, of course, is also present in Christian and pagan inscriptions.¹⁷ The exceptional terms employed to commemorate the dead son in line 7, ἀμμομω and ὁσεῖω, however, are more likely to have Jewish origins. Rutgers’ epigraphic tables, combined with those compiled by Antonio E. Felle for the series *Inscriptiones Christianae Urbis Romae*, confirm that while the archaic term ὁσιος is scarcely used in Christian inscriptions - and two of the five examples where it is found, ICUR 1.00132 and ICUR 4.12867, could be read as Jewish - it appears no less than fourteen times in Jewish epitaphs, a significant percentage of the six hundred or so epitaphs recognized as Jewish from the cemeteries of Rome.¹⁸ The success of ὁσιος in a Jewish funerary context may have come from its frequent and preferential use in the Septuagint. The Christians at Rome, on their part,

¹⁰ CIJ 1.283/JIWE 2.535 was found by Giovanni Marangoni on the second mile of the via Appia and given to the Jesuit Kircherian Museum in Rome. It is published for the first time by Lupi, 1734, pp. 177-178, from a drawing of Father Contuccio Contucci, S.J.

¹¹ See the bibliography accompanying this paper for a new bibliography on CIJ 1.1. P. Wesseling, and later Kirchoff, in CIG 4, p. 278, thought the piece could be Christian; see A. Ferrua, *Sulle Tombe dei Cristiani e quelle degli Ebrei*, in *Civiltà Cattolica* 2.5 (1936) p. 136.

¹² D. Noy, *Jewish Inscriptions in Western Europe, 2: The city of Rome*, Cambridge, 1995, p. 440, n. 556 (“unknown provenance”), and 470/618, from the Monteverde cemetery.

¹³ L. V. Rutgers, *The Jews of Late Ancient Rome: Evidence of Cultural Interaction in the Roman Diaspora*, Brill, 1995, pp. 192-193 and p. 198, where he states “the word ὁσιος, in particular, must have had special meaning for Roman Jews.”

¹⁴ C. Vismara, “I cimiteri ebraici di Roma” in A. Giardina, ed., *Società romana e impero tardoantico*, 2, Rome/Bari, 1986, tav. B.

¹⁵ Noy, 1995, p. 624 (CIG 3 no. 6615).

¹⁶ H. Solin, *Die Griechischen Personennamen in Rom: ein namenbuch*, 2, Berlin-New York, 1982, p. 281, of uncertain date, perhaps 3d century. P. M. Fraser and E. Matthews in the *Lexicon of Greek Personal Names 1: Aegean Islands, Cyprus and Cyrenaica*, Oxford, 1987, list an Ἀμέλιος at Cyrene in an inscription dated to the fourth-fifth centuries CE.

¹⁷ *Contra* Rutgers, 1995, table 2a, p. 195, where the parents’ names are listed as Latin and Semitic.

¹⁸ Rutgers, 1995, pp. 192-193, table 4, discussion p. 194; A. E. Felle, 1997, nn. 1339, 12867, 00312, 1385.b, 26492.

seem to have employed more frequently the expression ἅγιος (almost always in the phrase μετά των αγίων) that is found in the books of the New Testament.¹⁹ Ὅσιος does occur, however, in epitaphs that are not

included among the Jewish and Christian epitaphs from Rome.²⁰ Also present in the Septuagint - notably at the beginning of Psalm 118 - is the singular term ἄμωμος, or “blameless.” Variations of this term are found in a few other sepulchral texts in the Jewish catacombs of the Vigna Randanini: (CIJ 1.93/JIWE 2.209, CIJ 1.154/JIWE 2.227) as well as in a number of Christian epitaphs also from Rome, one, by coincidence, in the Palazzo Rondinini, where CIJ 1.1 is now found.²¹ Yet the spelling of these personal attributes in CIJ 1.1 appears unique among all the Greek texts from Rome.

The neutrality of the text of CIJ 1, 1 also may be workshop influenced: today we see that Winkelmann’s “urn of poor workmanship” is, in fact, a small marble sarcophagus, more or less intact. The front of this container is decorated with human and animal figures flanking a large rectangular tablet at center that contains the epitaph to Ἀμέλις. Although an exceptional iconographic and epigraphic find, and still conserved within the Palazzo Rondinini (or Rondanini) in Rome, the sarcophagus has attracted little attention and study until very recently.²²

A cloud of obscurity surrounds even its acquisition. A number of eighteenth century antiquarians took note of sarcophagi in the “Villa Sinibaldi” (or Falcone Sinibaldi) outside the Porta del Popolo in the area of the Villa Giulia that during the late sixteenth and seventeenth centuries had been the site of the celebrated gardens of the Cesi family of Aquasparta, and known to have been lavishly decorated with loggias, monumental staircases, fountains, and numerous statues and other antiques.²³ Many of these pieces were eventually acquired by major collections in Rome, including the Capitoline Museums.²⁴ Shortly after the Sinibaldi family abandoned the site in 1798, Giuseppe Valadier restored

¹⁹ Rutgers, 1995, p. 188; M. Guarducci, *Epigrafia Greca*, 4, Rome, 1978, p. 325, note 1. I am also indebted to Gregory DiPippo for a discussion of these terms.

²⁰ L. Moretti, *Inscriptiones Graecae Urbis Romae*, 2.1 (IGUR), Rome, 1968, no. 424, pp. 77-79. The term is used more often by Jews than Christians, but is also found in a small number of inscriptions not identified as either Christian or Jewish.

²¹ Felle, 1997, p. 10: 6 Christian texts include ἄμωμος. G. Migliore, in Cod. Vat. Lat. 9143, *Ad inscriptionem Flaviae Antoninae: commentarius, sive de antiquis Judaeis Italicis Exercitatio Epigraphica: prolegomena*, f. 117, also notes, in reference to another inscription in the Rondinini collection: “atque in ipso titulo initio filii nomen Amelios ultro cuius in quid incurrit. In inscriptione apud Marchionem Rondaninium, atque in Museo Clementino habeo ἄμωμος.”

²² A catalogue of marble artifacts in the Palazzo Rondanini was compiled by E. Paribeni and published as an appendix in L. Sarno’s *Palazzo Rondanini*, Rome, 1960. CIJ 1.1 discussed on pp. 268-269, n. 105, fig. 170. The photograph accompanying Paribeni’s entry was republished by G. Koch in *Fruhhrstliche Sarkophage*, Munchen, 2000, pp. 196, fig. 217. Koch includes the piece in the chapter on Jewish sarcophagi, despite the problem of assigning a Jewish identity to the piece. I am most grateful to Prof. Fabrizio Bisconti for calling my attention to this publication. Koch’s work is cited at length by Bruto and Ferro in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011. pp. 216-218 (n. 233).

²³ For possible work by B. Peruzzi on the site for Pope Julius III during the second half of the sixteenth century see Isa Belli Barsali, *Ville di Roma e di Lazio*, Milan, 1970, p. 67. A description and history of the Villa Cesi gardens is also found in Luccini & Pallavicini, 1981, pp. 48-52. G. Vasi, *Delle Magnificenze di Roma Antica e Moderna*, 10, Rome, 1761, p. 17, t. 186, mentions statues and fountains still inside the Sinibaldi estate.

²⁴ Belli Barsali, 1970, p. 11 (quote of De Sebastiani, *Viaggio Curioso dei Palazzi e Ville piu’ notabili di Roma*, Rome, 1683, p. 59).

the villa for its new owner, Prince Stanislaus Poiniatowski.²⁵ A brief inventory of the property in 1821 lists the statues, inscriptions and architectural fragments then on display, originating from Rome and many other areas, including excavations in Hadrian's Villa, Ostia and Sicily.²⁶ Yet no piece fits the description of the sarcophagus of Ἀμέλις, which must have already been sold to the Rondinini family by that time.

On its part, the Rondinini collection once numbered over 200 pieces, many acquired by the Marquis Giuseppe Rondinini during the second half of the eighteenth century.²⁷ It included several Jewish artifacts (CIJ 1 nn. 502, 520, 733c?) copied by Gaetano Migliore and others (including Marini, Winkelmann, and Reifferscheid) in the marquis' "casa-museo" on the via del Corso. The Kircherian Museum at the Collegio Romano later obtained the "Jewish" pieces seen today in the collection of the National Roman Museum. Yet there is too little evidence at present to connect these artifacts to the Jewish catacombs in the Vigna Randanini (or Rondanini) on the Appian Way, only identified as Jewish in 1859.²⁸ Before the mid-nineteenth century, the only published source for Jewish artifacts in Rome were the catacombs on the Monteverde first described by Antonio Bosio in 1632. Even then, however, some eighteenth century scholars, including Marini and Migliore, did not automatically attribute all the Jewish artifacts to one site. The *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum* indicates, in fact, that much of the Rondanini collection was purchased from antiquarians (including Jacopo Bellotti, a noted dealer in both real and fake antiquities) and other family collections (including that of the Giustiniani).²⁹ The sarcophagus of Ἀμέλις could have arrived through these channels to the Palazzo Rondinini, for Rondinini was fully seized by a mania for collecting at the time the Villa Sinibaldi was sold.³⁰

At this time, to the nobility and influential members of the Roman Catholic Church hierarchy, an antiquities collection with Jewish pieces was held in high esteem (only about 50 Jewish artifacts were then known).³¹ Jewish artifacts of particular note belonged to the Rusconi and Capponi families and to the Abbot Pennacchi: others could be seen in the monasteries of San Gregorio on the Caelian Hill and San Paolo fuori le Mura. Most in demand were the marble inscriptions and other objects (lamps, gold-glasses) that displayed clear "Jewish" signs like mention of a synagogue, a Hebrew acclamation, and/or decoration of the piece with objects associated with Jewish festivals and beliefs. For this reason, the pieces themselves

²⁵ Belli Barsani, 1970, p. 79, note 94; Cesare Sinibaldi had sold the estate to Antonio Candelori in 1798. In 1800, it was again sold, this time to the Polish prince Stanislaus Poiniatowski.

²⁶ *Indicazione degli oggetti piu' interessanti esistenti nella Villa posta fuori la Porta Flaminia spettante a Sua Altezza il Sig. Principe Poiniatowski*, Rome, 1821. There are many general references to ancient objects "nei muri e pilastri" of the buildings in this villa.

²⁷ For the creation of this collection, see Daniela Candilio, "La collezione di antichita' di Palazzo Rondinini" in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011, pp. 3-13; Marina Bertinetti, "La raccolta epigrafica di Palazzo Rondinini", pp. 13-26; and Brigitte Kuhn-Forte, "Formazione e dispersione della raccolta dei marmi antichi Rondinini", pp. 27-49.

²⁸ *Contra* M. Spaelli, *Museo Nazionale Romano: Le sculture*, 1, 10, Rome, 1988, p. 100, n. 116, and Bruto & Ferro in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011, pp. 218-219. The vineyard below which the Jewish catacomb had been found was not one of the known properties of the Rondinini family in the eighteenth century (records suggest it was first rented by one Giuseppe Randanini just before the discovery of the Jewish catacombs in 1859).

²⁹ We know from a note of Giovanni Cristoforo Amaduzzi that Bellotti once possessed one of two known copies of CIJ 380: Vat. Lat. Ferraiolj 415 f. 231 (Roma 17 aprile 1763).

³⁰ The CIL 6.3 identifies nn. 23092 and 26121 as acquired by the Rondinini family from the Villa Sinibaldi, the Vigna Moroni and Vigna Casali, respectively.

³¹ A. Ferrua, 1936, p. 127, criticizes the lack of documentation of these inscriptions in Rome before the discovery of the Vigna Randanini catacomb in 1859.

also needed to have a certain value in terms of the material used and the level of workmanship employed (no mention is made of the preservation and display of the more common but poorly-executed Jewish epitaphs incised or painted on plaster and mortar). The Rondinini “Judaica” collection soon became one of the largest of its time; so extensive, in fact, that studies continued to attribute Jewish artifacts to the site long after the palace itself and nearly all its Jewish artifacts had been sold.³²

The Jewish epitaphs in the Rondinini collection might have been on display with 80 or so other inscriptions on the walls of the inner courtyard of the Palazzo Rondinini (where a number of pieces are still found). The sarcophagus of Ἀμέλις, on the other hand, ended up in the “loggia a vetri” above this courtyard. An inventory of the palace’s possessions after the Marquis Rondinini’s death in 1801 identifies six small sarcophagi on this terrace, “in parte istoriati e in parte baccellati di mediocre maniera,” (echoes of Winkelmann!), all of “poverissimo” workmanship.³³ Such a low monetary value was assigned to the entire group that they remained on-site as palace furnishings after most of the other works of art were sold. The Ἀμέλις sarcophagus now doubles as a planter on the left side of the inner wall of the “loggia dei vetri” on the piano nobile of the private apartments of the gentlemen’s club Nuovo Circolo degli Scacchi.

The sarcophagus, marble grayish in tone, is roughly oval in shape, with rounded sides. It measures 1.27 m. in length, 27 cm. in height, and 13 cm in width.³⁴ The lid is now missing, and some damage has been done to the piece from a later use or arrangement, including holes in the back and right corner, and a large chip on the bottom right.³⁵ The sides of the casket remain, for the most part, in an unfinished state. That at left does have some rough indications, perhaps, of a rocky landscape, but the right side is pared down and smooth. There are no signs of restoration to the surface of the piece.

The front is decorated with several human and animal figures that flank a great rectangular tablet at center. The tablet measures 24 cm. by 18.5 cm. and is framed by a thick cornice (maximum 3 cm. on the upper left, minimum 2 cm. on the lower right).³⁶ The actual space for the text measures 23 cm. by 22 cm. The last two lines of text are added on the lower band of the cornice and the space between the tablet and bottom of the sarcophagus (4.2 cm). To add these lines, the stonemason carved back the bottom part of the cornice and base of the surrounding sculpted reliefs (cropping feet, the ends of tunics, and other features).

The first six lines of text, with the exception of line 4, are inserted almost perfectly into the surface of the tablet, each measuring more or less 22 cm. The extra lines run to extremes, especially for the crowded line 7 on the cornice: 27 cm. to 18 cm. (the one word on line 8). The letters range from a minimum of 1.2 (εἰώ in line 7) to a 2.5 cm. maximum (τ in line 2). Ample space is left between the words in lines 2-4, with one triangular inter-punctuation in line 4 between ας and β. Winkelmann added others after τᾶτω in line 2 and β in line 4, which are not apparent in this version of the text (and possibly his own corrections). Individual letters are legible and carved with regularity, even with stylistic flourishes like the tails on the β, the curved script of β and η. These details suggest that the

³² Until very recently, the “Seasons Sarcophagus” now in the collection of the Museo Nazionale Romano was mistakenly attributed to the Rondinini. Raffaele Garrucci, S.J, attributes the inscription CIJ 1.497/JIWE 2.539 to the Rondinini collection, even when it was discovered in 1843; see R. Garrucci, “Alcune iscrizioni di cimiteri giudaici diversi,” in *Dissertazioni Archeologiche di Vario Argomento* 2, Rome, (1864-1865) p. 191, n. 3.

³³ Sarno, 1960, p. 312: inventory of Carlo Albacini, August 13th, 1807, (divisione delle statue) “salendo vari gradini vi e’ un altra loggia ove in vari lati sono posti n. 6 piccoli sarcofagi parte istoriati e parte baccellati di mediocre maniera assieme li valutano 20.” G. Marini copied ninety-three inscriptions “della loggia e cortile.” The sarcophagus of Ἀμέλις must have been inventoried as a “sculpture,” and therefore no note was taken of the inscription and its possible Jewish attribution.

³⁴ Bruto, in Candilio & Bertinetti, p. 216, gives the measurements as height 31 cm.; length 1.27 m.; depth (of the container) 30 cm.

³⁵ Bruto, in Candilio & Bertinetti, p. 216, also notes that the right hand of one of the figures which overlaps with the central *tabella* for the inscription has been broken off.

³⁶ Some of these measurements are confirmed by Ferro in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011, p. 217 (n. 233).

stonecutter had some familiarity or practice with Greek script. Lupi's difficulties with the transcription of lines 5 and 7 are due to the narrow spacing between the letters on these lines. As discussed above, some words are shortened, while others have an extra letter repeated or added (ἔζζησεν, ἀμμωμῶ and ὀσεῖω). These cases are so singular that they cannot be considered generic/standard treatments of the formulae and attributes they express.

The decoration around the text is on a single band, dominated by four figures nearly as tall as the central panel. The carving technique used to render these figures is closer to that found on the lids of sarcophagi than the more finished and proportionately designed works of this type often imported to Rome.

At the far left, beside what might be seen as a "rocky slope" in descent, is the profile of a dog facing right behind an outcropping of rock. A figure in a toga is seated on the top of this small mountain, reading an open scroll (*rotulus*) in his hands. The head is enormous (the ears in particular), very disproportionate to the body, and accentuated by the long hair and deep grooves around the head and upper back. The drapes of the toga are indicated with thin folds. Directly in front, also facing the tablet at right is another long-haired figure, exhibiting similar youthful traits. Shown with his left foot on a small rock, the individual delivers a speech, gesturing with his hands. The hands slightly overlap with the left side of the cornice at center. On the right side, also overlapping with the tablet, is another boyish figure, probably always the same individual, now pictured with his right arm wrapped in a mantle and grasping its folds over the left shoulder.³⁷ An object - perhaps a scroll or container - dangles loosely from the left hand.³⁸ The last human figure, on the extreme right, departs from the realism of the other scenes of reading, discourse and instruction. The body of the last figure is in a more frontal position, and has distinctly feminine traits. The deep groove encircling the head resembles the Oriental nimbus, a curious feature for a figure shown perched on the back of a peacock, with both hands outstretched in a gesture close to that of an *orant*.³⁹ Behind the head of the peacock, the surface of the sarcophagus has been pared down and made smooth, except for a hole drilled into the upper right.

As funerary art, these scenes appear to form an extremely spiritual composition that still owes much to the Classical tradition although the technique of execution suggests a much later date.⁴⁰ In a Jewish context, at least in that of funerary material produced for the Jews of Rome, this piece is exceptional. Its figures seem to "interpret" the actual text, depicting the deceased, a young child, studying, declaiming, and living his "holy" and "immaculate" life before an early death and journey to Paradise.⁴¹ As the *cursus vitae* of a child, the series of figures is already singular; if demonstrated to be genuine and related to the life of a young Jew, the scenes will provoke a controversy in scholarship not easily or unanimously resolved.

Several theories immediately present themselves. That most likely is that the sarcophagus is a fantastic creation of the seventeenth or eighteenth centuries, perhaps incorporating a "real" or authentic inscription (or a fake one with obvious "mistakes"); another "Jewish" piece, CIJ 1.380/JIWE 2.557, of unknown provenance, is known to have existed in multiple copies at this time.⁴² The sarcophagus's

³⁷ Bruto, in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011, p.216, however, identifies two of these figures (those on the far right & left) as "muses", proposing only the two figures on either side of the *tabella* as representations of the deceased.

³⁸ Bruto, in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011, p. 216, identifies this as a collection of "*tabulae dealbatae o ceratae*", typically used by young students in Ancient Rome.

³⁹ Bruto, in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011, p. 216, identifies this feminine figure as a muse.

⁴⁰ Koch, 2000, p. 593 proposes the second half of the fourth century CE (also Sarno, 1960, p. 274). Bruto in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011, p. 217, suggest an early fourth century date. Noy, 1995, p. 440, from the text only, dates the inscription to the third-fourth centuries CE.

⁴¹ The theme of the *cursus vitae* and symbols of immortality are discussed by Bruto in Candilio & Bertinetti, 2011, p. 216.

⁴² According to Noy, 1995, p. 440, one version of this inscription is still preserved in Naples' Archaeological Museum.

irregularities in cut and decoration also favor a modern origin, as does Winkelmann's bland description, possibly made before the piece was "improved upon" by one of Rome's many artisans to fetch a higher price. On the other hand, if ancient, it may not be "Jewish" at all, but rather created for a non-Jewish client. The title *archon*, although commonly used for Jewish individuals in Rome, was never in itself exclusive to Jews, and could refer to a leader of one of the many other communities in Rome at the time, including the Mithraic sect.⁴³

Long ignored or missing until the mid-twentieth century, the sarcophagus needs to be examined more closely to determine its authenticity and relationship to the collection and study of Jewish antiquities in eighteenth-century Rome.

Bibliography

- A. M. Lupi, *Dissertatio ed animadversiones ad nuper inventum Severae Martyris epitaphium*, Palermo, 1734, p. 140.
- P. Wesseling, *Diatriba de Judaeorum Archontibus ad Inscriptionem Berenicensem*, 1738, col. 1204.
- L. A. Muratori, *Novus Thesaurus veterum inscriptionum*, 2, Milan, 1740, p. 1129, n. 6.
- E. Corsini, *Notae Graecorum, Appendix 2*, Florence, 1749.
- J. J. Winkelmann, *Ville e Palazzi di Roma: 1756*, ed. J. R. Serra, Rome, 2000, p. 200.
- G. Piacentini, *de siglis veterum graecorum, Rome*, 1757, p. 33.
- V. Giovenazzi, *della Citta' di Abeja ne' Vestini*, Rome, 1773, p. 57.
- G. Migliore, Cod. Vat. Lat. 9143, *Ad inscriptionem Flaviae Antoninae: commentarius, sive de antiquis Judaeis Italicis Exercitatio Epigraphica: prolegomena*, esp. 116 v. - 117 r.
- Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum* 3, ed. Kirchoff, Berlin, 1859, p. 947 n. 6337, vol 4, p. 278.
- R. Garrucci, *Dissertazioni Archeologiche di Vario Argomento 2*, Rome, 1866, p. 186, n. 1.
- G. B. De Rossi (1850's-1890's), Cod. Vat. Lat. XL, n. 16149.
- J-B Frey, *Corpus Inscriptionum Judicarum* 1, Vatican City, 1936, p. 6, n. 1.
- A. Ferrua, "Addenda et Corrigenda al Corpus Inscriptionum Judicarum" in *Epigraphica* 3, 1941, pp. 30-46.
- H. J. Leon, *Jews of Ancient Rome*, New York, 1960, p. 264, n. 1.
- C. Vismara, "I ciminteri ebraici di Roma" in A. Giardina, ed., *Societa' romana e impero tardoantico*, 2, Rome/Bari, 1986, p. 359, n. 122.
- A. Konikoff, *Sarcophagi from the Jewish Catacombs of Ancient Rome: a catalogue raisonne*, 2d ed., Stuttgart, 1990.
- D. Noy, *Jewish Inscriptions of Western Europe 2: the City of Rome*, Cambridge, 1995, pp. 439-440 (n. 556).
- A. E. Felle, *Inscriptiones Christianae Urbis Romae nova series: concordantiae verborum, nominum et imaginem: tituli graeci*, Bari, 1997.
- G. Wilpert, *Sarcophagi Cristiani* 1, tav 3.
- L. Sarno, *Palazzo Rondanini*, with a catalogue of the ancient marbles by E. Paribeni, Rome, 1960, pp. 268-269 (n. 105).
- G. Koch, *Fruhchristliche Sarkophage*, Munich, 2000, p. 193, fig. 217.
- G. Koch, "Judische Sarkophage der Kaiserzeit un der Spatantike" in *What Athens has to do with Jerusalem*, ed. L. V. Rutgers, Leuven, 2002, pp. 190-200.
- M. L. Bruto – C. Ferro, "Sarcofago a lenos con iscrizione sepolcrale del fanciullo Ἀμῆλιος" in *I Marmi Antichi del Palazzo Rondanini*, ed. D. Candilio & M. Bertinetti, Rome, 2011, pp. 216-218 (n. 233).

⁴³ I am indebted to PIAC classmate Dr. Alessandra Negroni for suggesting a possible connection between the title of *archon* and the cult of Mithras.